

1 The Virtual Ship Classroom: Developing 2 Virtual Fieldwork as an Authentic Learning 3 Environment for Physical Oceanography

4 Abstract

5 Typical physical oceanography fieldwork involves boarding a research vessel and
6 traveling to the open ocean for periods of up to several weeks. Such scientific research
7 expeditions are expensive, time-consuming, logistically challenging, and therefore are
8 not very accessible. We present design-based research about an alternative: a virtual
9 fieldwork experience using the new VirtualShip Python package and accompanying
10 lesson materials. Data are collected in two graduate courses using qualitative and
11 quantitative methods, and includes interviews, surveys, and grading rubrics to
12 investigate students' learning outcomes and learning experience. We find that the virtual
13 fieldwork was highly engaging, and students report on enhanced self-efficacy and
14 knowledge. We conclude that student involvement and learning were boosted by using
15 the Virtual Ship Classroom as an authentic learning environment.

16 Keywords (6)

17 Virtual fieldwork, sea-based research, design-based research, technology-enhanced
18 learning, higher education, authentic learning

19 1. Introduction

20 Scientific research expeditions are a key part of oceanography, but these multi-
21 day expeditions to the open ocean are carbon-intensive and expensive; also, competition
22 for ship time is often fierce, so most expeditions are necessarily multi-institutional,
23 international, and often multidisciplinary. Ship size restrictions and expedition cost can
24 lead to restricted accessibility and participation for oceanography students and early
25 career researchers (Barnhill et al. 2023). Despite logistical challenges, such as the
26 number of berths on board that restrict the number of participants, it is important to
27 provide the next generation of oceanographers with appropriate fieldwork skills (Barnhill
28 et al. 2023) because seagoing experience is often viewed as an essential part of the
29 foundation for a career in at-sea oceanography (Gunn & Thomsen 2009).

30 Alternatives for students to gain similar experience are, for example,
31 telepresence, serious games (Koenigstein et al. 2020; Mayer et al. 2014), and virtual
32 fieldwork (Gerringer et al. 2023; Glenn et al. 2011). Virtual fieldwork and the related field
33 guides are modern methodologies which offer opportunities to explore an area and
34 environment without leaving the classroom by using computers and dedicated software
35 packages (Firomumwe 2022). Virtual fieldwork is a relatively new concept and often
36 incorporates Virtual Reality. As such, it has the potential to offer many benefits to
37 students, such as being more inclusive (i.e., being accessible for all students), building
38 student skills and confidence, and increasing engagement in the topic studied (Cliffe
39 2017). Virtual fieldwork seems like a great opportunity for students to learn field skills
40 they would otherwise gain from a scientific research expedition.

41 In this paper, we present the first two cycles of a design-based research (DBR)
42 study on the “Virtual Ship Classroom”: a virtual fieldwork experience for (physical)
43 oceanography. DBR combines empirical educational research with theory-driven design
44 in learning contexts to understand how, when, and why educational innovations work in
45 real settings (T. Anderson & Shattuck 2012). The main characteristic of DBR is the
46 systematic and iterative cycle of design, exploration, and redesign (Design-Based
47 Research Collective 2003). Before designing our fieldwork, we analyzed and identified
48 gaps in student knowledge and skills and formulated intended learning outcomes in

49 collaboration with instructors and oceanography experts. The learning outcomes are
50 aligned using verbs from the revised version of Bloom's taxonomy (L. Anderson et al.
51 2001).

52 The Virtual Ship Classroom is supported by a new Python package, VirtualShip.
53 Our DBR focuses on graduate level (European MSc program) courses, because that
54 student cohort has the most experience with coding and virtual environments. Even if
55 students have not worked with Python before, we expect these students to pick up a
56 (new) programming language quickly. As we continue to develop the VirtualShip package,
57 we aim to reduce the necessary background knowledge in Python for the Virtual Ship
58 Classroom to also be useful in undergraduate (and even secondary education) courses.

59 We designed the virtual fieldwork as an authentic learning environment (J.
60 Herrington et al. 2013; T. Herrington & J. Herrington 2005) with the objective of engaging
61 students to increase their learning experience. An authentic learning environment should
62 reflect actual practices that reflect the way knowledge will be used in real life. A review of
63 the literature on authentic learning established a model with the following four themes:

- 64 1. The activity involves real-world problems that mimic the work of professionals.
- 65 2. Open-ended inquiry, thinking skills, and metacognition are addressed.
- 66 3. Students engage in discourse and social learning in a community of learners,
- 67 4. Students are empowered through choice to direct their own learning in relevant
68 project work.

69 Considering these themes helped us design and improve our virtual fieldwork.

70 In this paper, we present the design rationale for the Virtual Ship Classroom and
71 our initial findings regarding its impact on student learning outcomes and experiences.
72 We designed, implemented, and evaluated an intervention in two graduate courses for
73 physical oceanography following a mixed-methods approach. The data include
74 interviews, surveys, rubrics, and student notebooks, which are triangulated to assess
75 students' learning outcomes and experiences, and to evaluate the suitability of our virtual
76 fieldwork as an authentic learning environment. Specifically, our study addresses the
77 following research question:

78 *RQ: To what extent does the Virtual Ship Classroom serve as an authentic learning*
79 *environment that reflects real-world oceanographic research practices, and how does it*
80 *impact students' learning outcomes and experiences?*

81 The rest of the paper is structured as follows. In section 2, we describe our
82 methodological approach, context and design rationale for the development of the
83 Virtual Ship Classroom. In section 3, we present the results of our study in the respective
84 design cycles. Our final section, 4, includes discussion and a conclusion, the limitations
85 of our study and avenues for future work.

86 2. Methodology

87 2.1 Design-based research stages

88 Following the DBR methodology described by Reeves (2006), our study involved
89 three stages. In stage 1, we conducted semi-structured interviews with experts in
90 physical oceanography to identify gaps in student knowledge and skills and formulated
91 the intended learning outcomes. We also had discussions with course instructors at this
92 stage, to formulate the intended learning outcomes of the Virtual Ship Classroom. Then,
93 in stage 2, we designed the virtual fieldwork and accompanying lesson materials with the
94 researchers in collaboration with course instructors. Stage 3 involved the testing and
95 refinement of the iterative cycles in practice. Qualitative and quantitative data were
96 collected during two cycles using various instruments: student surveys, semi-structured
97 interviews, rubrics filled in by instructors, and notebooks handed in by students. The
98 collected data focused on exploring the student's learning experience and learning
99 outcomes, and it guided us in improving the design of the next iteration. Note that we did
100 not perform stage 4 of a typical DBR cycle, the distillation of prominent Design Principles,
101 as the two cycles on which we tested the Virtual Ship Classroom did not provide
102 sufficiently diverse data yet.

103 2.1.1 Stage 1: Formulate intended learning outcomes

104 Our virtual fieldwork encourages deeper learning and enables students to engage in
105 higher-order thinking processes such as applying, analysing, evaluating, and creating

106 new knowledge. The intended learning outcomes are formulated so that at the end of the
107 virtual fieldwork, students can:

- 108 • Recognize and address practical challenges involved in planning sea-based
109 research by combining foundational knowledge from lectures and personal
110 observations during the virtual fieldwork (Bloom Level 1 and 4).
- 111 • Understand and reflect on the uncertainty and variability inherent in sea-based
112 observations (Bloom Level 4).
- 113 • Analyze and interpret sea-based observations in Python, and are able to (Bloom
114 Level 4):
 - 115 ○ Read in different data formats.
 - 116 ○ Manipulate arrays and other data formats.
 - 117 ○ Contribute to a report with text and plots.
- 118 • Plan a comprehensive research expedition, and are able to (Bloom Level 6):
 - 119 ○ Formulate a relevant research question.
 - 120 ○ Select appropriate sampling sites and equipment.
 - 121 ○ Account for deployment durations and logistical constraints.

122 2.1.2 Stage 2: Design (rationale) of the Virtual Ship Classroom

123 We designed the virtual fieldwork as an authentic learning environment (J. Herrington et
124 al. 2013; T. Herrington & J. Herrington 2005) aiming to improve students' learning
125 experience. There are ten design characteristics of authentic activities in literature
126 (Reeves et al. 2002). For designers of authentic activities, these characteristics can
127 provide a useful checklist. In Table 1, we provide an overview of the characteristics of
128 authentic activities and their corresponding implementations in the Virtual Ship
129 Classroom.

Authentic Activity Characteristic	Implementation in the Virtual Ship Classroom
Real-World Relevance	Tasks align with real-world oceanographer activities, such as reading instrument data and calculating derived quantities like ocean current transports.

Ill-Defined Tasks	Students define their unique tasks and sub-tasks by starting with their own research question or hypothesis, mirroring the open-ended nature of real-world scientific inquiry.
Complex Tasks over Time	Activities span hours to weeks, requiring significant time and intellectual investment to simulate sustained scientific investigation.
Multiple Perspectives and Resources	Students use diverse resources to answer research questions, enhancing their ability to discern relevant from irrelevant methods.
Collaborative Opportunities	Collaboration was essential, particularly in Cycle 2, where teamwork enabled the timely delivery of an end product, reflecting real-world team dynamics.
Reflection Opportunities	Students experimented with data collection and reflected on whether their chosen measurement strategies adequately addressed their research questions.
Cross-Disciplinary Integration	The Virtual Ship Classroom, while initially focused on physical oceanography, can be adapted for subjects like marine biology or geochemistry, fostering interdisciplinary learning.
Seamless Integration with Assessment	Students' final presentations simulate real-world assessment practices, providing an authentic evaluation experience.
Creation of Polished, Reusable Products	Using Jupyter notebooks, students produce an end-product that is practical, polished, and easily reusable for future reference or application.
Support for Competing Solutions and Diverse Outcomes	Freedom to choose regions of interest and formulate research questions allows a diversity of approaches and solutions, reflecting the complexity of real-world scientific problems.

130 *Table 1. Virtual Ship Classroom as an Authentic Learning Environment according to*
131 *Reeves et al. (2002).*

132 Guided by the themes and activity characteristics above, the development and
133 refinement of the Virtual Ship Classroom focuses on creating didactically sound,
134 authentic learning experiences grounded in established learning theories in science
135 education, such as constructivism (Piaget 1954) and constructionism (Papert 1980). By
136 integrating realistic tasks and a gamified narrative approach within Jupyter notebooks,
137 students learn within a digital replica of the real world, constructing knowledge through
138 ‘learning by doing’ and ‘trial and error’ as they explore oceanography concepts, research
139 methods, and analysis tools.

140 The principle of “low floors, wide walls, and high ceilings” (Resnick et al. 2005), tailored
141 to a higher education context, is central to our design. The Virtual Ship Classroom
142 provides accessible entry points using simple Jupyter notebooks (low floors), while also
143 supporting deeper, more complex exploration and analysis in later stages. Even though
144 students attending the course are expected to have sufficient skills in Python
145 programming, scaffolding elements support learners to cover potential knowledge gaps
146 and advance toward more complex data analysis and computational derivations (high
147 ceilings).

148 The virtual fieldwork also allows students to develop their own unique research questions
149 and choose their own oceanic region or phenomenon of interest, which makes their
150 learning experience more relevant to their personal and professional aspirations and
151 interests (wide walls). Accessibility is a key element of our design rationale. Students can
152 learn at their own pace and take responsibility for diverse tasks within group projects.
153 Scaffolding elements, including tutorials, videos, snippets, and introductory exercises
154 support students who may start the course with knowledge gaps or limited Python
155 programming experience. The material is fully open source, making it widely
156 customizable and accessible to diverse audiences.

157 Lastly, collaborative learning is actively encouraged, with abundant opportunities for
158 peer interaction, knowledge exchange, and sharing of expertise within groupwork
159 settings. By taking responsibility for various tasks across virtual expeditions, students
160 can experience a group dynamic that mirrors real-world scientific environments, where

161 interdisciplinary collaboration and collective effort are essential for successful research.
162 This approach not only fosters oceanography content knowledge and practical skills but
163 also helps students develop essential soft skills, such as teamwork, communication,
164 and project management, preparing them for professional research settings.

165 *2.1.2.1 The Virtual Ship Classroom setup*

166 Technically, the virtual fieldwork consists of a Python tool (VirtualShip) and
167 accompanying notebooks containing the lesson material, combinedly called the “Virtual
168 Ship Classroom”. The Python tool is based on Parcels v3 (Delandmeter & van Sebille
169 2019) and samples the Copernicus Global Ocean Physics Analysis and Forecast dataset
170 (GOPAF 2024) in such a way that the output closely resembles the datafiles that are
171 generated by the equipment onboard research vessels. The material is open source and
172 available online: github.com/OceanParcels/virtualship.

173 In preparation for the virtual fieldwork, students are asked to create an expedition design
174 by planning the deployment of equipment so that the gathered data will allow them to
175 answer their research question. After the virtual expedition, students are expected to
176 visualize the data and explain their variability and (spatial) patterns.

177 Jupyter notebooks are central in our authentic learning environment. Notebooks are
178 interactive documents that contain code, equations, visualizations, and narrative text
179 that are widely used in the scientific community. The notebooks inform students about
180 preparing for a research expedition and introduce the scientific equipment in a narrative
181 approach to engage them (Naul & Liu 2019). We also use notebooks for scaffolding data
182 handling and analysis, for example, giving code snippets and practice exercises that use
183 similar data. The VirtualShip output can be analyzed by the students direct in their Jupyter
184 notebooks. To make sure the dependencies for the notebooks are met and they do not
185 behave in unexpected ways (Barba et al. 2022; Johnson 2020), the students are
186 instructed to use a predefined environment with the required software packages. The
187 newest version of the notebooks can be found here:
188 <https://virtualship.oceanparcels.org/en/latest/user-guide/tutorials/index.html>

189 **2.1.3 Stage 3: Testing iterations**

190 In stage 3, the iterative cycles of testing and refinement, the students interact with the
 191 virtual fieldwork. They follow authentic fieldwork steps in order (Table 2).

Step	Content	Cycle 1	Cycle 2
1	Introduction	X	X
2	Choose location		X
3	Formulate hypothesis		X
4	Write expedition plan	X	X
5	Perform simulation	X	X
6	Data analysis	X	X
7	Scientific presentation		X

192 *Table 2: The content covered in the two cycles of the testing of the Virtual Ship Classroom.*

193 In Cycle 1, we implemented the Virtual Ship Classroom in the MSc course Introduction
 194 to Physical Oceanography at Utrecht University. The students in this course usually have
 195 a background in biology or geosciences with little or no programming experience. One of
 196 the course goals is that the students “Have developed coding and data analysis skills
 197 using Python.” They therefore have a two-hour introductory Python workshop and weekly
 198 tutorials using Python. The students interacted with our material for 4 hours, spread over
 199 2 tutorials of 2 hours each. The students could choose whether to collaborate with a
 200 fellow student or work by themselves. The work was not graded. During the tutorials, a
 201 teaching assistant (TA) and the instructor were responsible for supporting students as
 202 needed. One researcher was present to assist, observe and take care of the overall
 203 execution of the tutorials.

204 In Cycle 2, we implemented the Virtual Ship Classroom in the MSc course Dynamical
 205 Oceanography at Utrecht University. The students in this course usually have a

206 background in physics or applied mathematics and have programming experience,
207 although not always in Python. The students interacted with the material for at least 20
208 hours, spread over 10 tutorials of 2 hours each in 6 weeks. The students were split into
209 groups of 3 to 4 students each and gave a presentation of their work at the end that was
210 graded by the instructor and one TA. During the tutorials, two or three TAs were
211 responsible for supporting students as needed. Two researchers were present to assist,
212 observe and take care of the overall execution of the tutorials.

213 Some differences between the cycles are that in Cycle 1, the virtual ship was only
214 equipped with 2 scientific instruments: an Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP; e.g.,
215 Kuroda et al. 1988) and a Conductivity-Temperature-Depth instrument (CTD; e.g., Xiao et
216 al. 2023). In Cycle 2, the students were also able to deploy up to 30 surface drifters (e.g.,
217 Lumpkin & Pazos 2005) and/or Argo floats (e.g., Wong et al. 2020) and sample underwater
218 data (e.g., Gaillard et al. 2015). In Cycle 1, the fieldwork was limited to the Tropical Pacific
219 Ocean as students were supposed to investigate the El Niño Southern Oscillation (e.g.,
220 Timmermann et al., 2018), while in Cycle 2 the students were able to choose from ten
221 regions that are both oceanographically interesting and sufficiently realistically
222 represented in the underlying dataset. In both cycles, students are introduced to the
223 concept of fieldwork in an engaging way; they plan the cruise, virtually measure ocean
224 fields with VirtualShip, and are guided on how to do data analysis (i.e., reading in,
225 manipulating, and visualizing the data).

226 2.2 Data collection and analysis

227 2.2.1 Student surveys

228 An online survey was distributed directly after each final class in which the virtual
229 fieldwork was used (see appendix). The survey included Likert scale questions on
230 engagement, knowledge and self-efficacy, and open questions on these topics and on
231 improvements. We used a five-point Likert scale to allow students to express how much
232 they agree or disagree with a particular statement. Approximately 20 surveys were
233 collected after each cycle.

234 2.2.2 Rubrics and notebooks

235 The rubrics used to grade the student presentations (Cycle 2 only), and the students'
236 notebooks were collected. We use the data for intercomparison between
237 students/groups and confirming the students self-reported learning. Notebooks of 21
238 students were collected in Cycle 1. Notebooks and rubrics were collected for 7 groups of
239 3-4 students each in Cycle 2. The structure of the notebooks was not sufficient to apply
240 quantitative analysis, but the content demonstrated student learning.

241 2.2.3 Student interviews

242 Semi-structured interviews based on an interview guide were conducted with students
243 within a week of completing the virtual fieldwork (see appendix). Each interview lasted
244 15 to 30 minutes. During the interviews, students were asked what skills/knowledge are
245 essential to have before doing the virtual fieldwork, to describe their engagement, to
246 explain what they learned during the project, and to share their suggestions for improving
247 the virtual fieldwork. Two students were interviewed after Cycle 1 and four students after
248 Cycle 2.

249 2.2.4 Instructor interviews

250 Semi-structured interviews based on an interview guide were conducted with instructors
251 within a week of the virtual fieldwork (see appendix). Each interview lasted 20 to
252 30 minutes. During the interviews, we asked instructors and teaching assistants about
253 their overall impression of the virtual fieldwork, what skills or knowledge students should
254 have when participating, what engagement of the students they observed, and their
255 suggestions for improving the virtual fieldwork. One instructor and one teaching assistant
256 (TA) were interviewed after Cycle 1, and one instructor and three TAs after Cycle 2.

257 2.2.5 Data analysis

258 Interviews were recorded, transcribed and anonymized. We analyzed the interviews and
259 open survey questions using both inductive and deductive approaches using NVivo 14
260 software (Mayring 2014). The deductive codes we used were engagement,
261 disengagement, self-efficacy, problems, highlights, prerequisites, and improvements.
262 Inductive codes were added during the analysis and combined with the deductive ones

263 to analyze the results and to identify overarching themes. Quotes are used in the results
 264 section to exemplify the interviews. To visualize the result of the student surveys, we use
 265 diverging bar charts.

266 3. Results

267 In this section, we present our results in terms of students' learning outcomes and
 268 learning experience and the suggested improvements for Cycle 1 and 2.

269 3.1 Cycle 1

270 3.1.1 Learning outcomes

271 Although learning Python is not an explicitly formulated learning outcome in this
 272 research, it is something that is required for the students and shows up throughout the
 273 data analyses. In Cycle 1, five students explicitly mentioned in the open questions of the
 274 survey that they improved their Python skills during the tutorials. In addition, the TA and
 275 more than half the students answered that programming skills are the main prerequisite
 276 for the virtual fieldwork. However, one student explained in the interview that they
 277 reported feeling less confident because they were now aware of not having sufficient
 278 Python skills, even though before they thought they would be able to do the task.

280 *Figure 1: The responses of the students in Cycle 1 concerning their knowledge and self-*
281 *efficacy for the learning outcomes, on a five-point Likert scale. Red bars represent*
282 *negative responses, grey bars represent neutral responses, and green bars represent*
283 *positive responses. Numbers in the bars denote the total number of responses for each*
284 *answer.*

285 As illustrated in Figure 1, it follows that the students generally report on improved
286 knowledge and self-efficacy in the learning outcomes. The notebooks confirm that most
287 students were able to plan a research cruise, select sampling sites, and create and
288 interpret CTD profiles using our scaffolding approach. The course instructor confirmed
289 that students increased their understanding of the subject from, e.g., interpreting the
290 (virtual) sea-based observations:

291 *“I think they probably got a better understanding of the four-dimensional aspects of what*
292 *happens in the ocean in terms of changes over time and then in the XYZ direction. I think*
293 *that. So, they see in the end back in the data, what is in the equations which they have*
294 *previously been discussing. So, it should help them to understand things.” [Interview*
295 *instructor]*

296 Additionally, engagement was used as a measure of achieving the learning outcomes,
297 because “student engagement is widely recognized as an important influence on
298 achievement and learning in higher education” (Kahu 2013). Engagement is easier to
299 observe and more reliable to self-report on than learning or motivation (Henrie et al.
300 2015). In the survey, the majority of students reported that they were at least as engaged
301 during the Virtual Ship Classroom tutorials as during the other tutorials of the course.
302 Only one student reported a lower level of engagement. Observations by the researcher,
303 the TA and the instructor confirm the high level of engagement among the students,
304 especially in the first tutorial. The hands-on approach of the authentic learning
305 environment and narrative writing style might explain the high level of engagement that
306 was reported and observed.

Cycle 1: Compared to the other tutorials, how was ... in the virtual ship classroom?

307

308 *Figure 2: The responses of the students in Cycle 1 concerning their learning experience,*
 309 *on a five-point Likert scale. Red bars represent negative responses, grey bars represent*
 310 *neutral responses, and green bars represent positive responses. Numbers in the bars*
 311 *denote the total number of responses for each answer.*

312 3.1.2 Learning experience

313 The virtual fieldwork was designed as an authentic learning environment by combining a
 314 narrative approach in the Jupyter notebooks with real tasks and freedom for the students
 315 to create their own experience (Figure 2). From the student’s perspective, drawing from
 316 the survey, it seems students appreciate the authentic learning environment. For
 317 example, in an open question on appreciation, five students answered they liked using
 318 real data and directly learning how to apply them. In addition, nine students said that they
 319 liked the creative scenario type of assignments. They answered for example: “*The way of*
 320 *writing, trying to stimulate real life scenarios*” and “*Hands-on learning by directly applying*
 321 *and using data. Therefore, it is very relevant*”. In an interview, a student explained:

322 *“I liked the whole like CTD thing. I think it's because to me it just feels like very, very*
 323 *practical knowledge to know. How many you have to do and how long you have to stop*
 324 *the boat and all that sort of stuff and all those things. And yeah, I like that. That's probably*
 325 *to me the thing that made it feel the most real.”* [Interview Student 2]

326 Furthermore, seven students in the open question on appreciation indicated they liked
 327 the assistance or the help of the teacher. The design and implementation of our
 328 scaffolding approach could well have contributed to the students’ learning experience.

329 3.1.3 Improvements

330 In Cycle 1, the virtual fieldwork could be done as an individual assignment. We, however,
 331 believe students learn more from collaboration. So, for Cycle 2, the assignments were

332 adapted to be groupwork, so students would examine different perspectives, discuss,
 333 reflect, and share information.

334 In addition, more images and video clips were added to the notebooks in Cycle 2. The TA
 335 in Cycle 1 thought this was very important, and both students mentioned it in the
 336 interviews. One suggested including more infographics, the other more video clips.

337 *“I think you should consider that these kids need more, something like social media. They
 338 need more media. They need more videos. They need more interactive game-like
 339 interactive sessions.”* [Interview TA]

340 3.2 Cycle 2

341 3.2.1 Learning outcomes

342 The students in Cycle 2 already have some programming experience. Nevertheless, four
 343 students explicitly mentioned in the open questions of the survey that they improved their
 344 Python skills during the tutorials. Two TAs and almost half of the students answered that
 345 programming skills are the main prerequisite for the virtual fieldwork.

347 *Figure 3: The responses of the students in Cycle 2 concerning their knowledge and self-*
 348 *efficacy for the learning outcomes, on a five-point Likert scale. Red bars represent*
 349 *negative responses, grey bars represent neutral responses, and green bars represent*
 350 *positive responses. Numbers in the bars denote the total number of responses for each*
 351 *answer.*

352 The majority of students answered in the survey that they probably or definitely felt more
 353 knowledgeable and/or confident about the learning outcomes of the virtual fieldwork
 354 (see Figure 3). That they did indeed gain skills and knowledge can be concluded from the
 355 presentations and the grading rubrics that were filled in during the presentations. All
 356 groups managed to conduct the virtual fieldwork, analyze and visualize their results,
 357 perform a derived analysis, and answer their research questions adequately. TA1 in the
 358 interview stressed that this was also due to the scaffolding approach.

359 *“So, I think that for students who don't have that much coding experience, there was a lot*
 360 *to learn and that paid off, I think. Because in the end nearly all students had some really*
 361 *adequate results. And I think that was really nice to see. That they sort of followed up on*
 362 *what we gave them and you could really see that they've learned a lot of new skills.”*
 363 [Interview TA1]

364 Generally, a high level of engagement was observed and mentioned in Cycle 2 by both the
 365 instructor and TAs in the interviews.

366 *“I feel like I remember a lot of students kind of just, yeah, really working on the exercises*
 367 *and kind of having a drive to want to solve the exercises.”* [Interview TA2]

368 *“I feel like they put a lot of effort into this and they didn't just want to get this over with, so*
 369 *it's not like learning for an exam where you... where your goal is to just learn for an exam*
 370 *and you're done, right. So, a lot of the students tried to kind of make this project their own,”*
 371 [Interview TA3]

373 *Figure 4: The responses of the students in Cycle 1 concerning their learning experience,*
374 *on a five-point Likert scale. Red bars represent negative responses, grey bars represent*
375 *neutral responses, and green bars represent positive responses. Numbers in the bars*
376 *denote the total number of responses for each answer.*

377 Results from the student survey (Figure 4) also confirm that the level of engagement
378 during the virtual ship was average or above for all the students. This could be due to the
379 authenticity of the virtual fieldwork, in which the students learning process started from
380 an ocean current or physical oceanographic phenomenon, and their own research
381 question about it. The large amount of freedom provided students with the opportunity
382 to examine the problem from different perspectives and there was no single correct
383 answer. The learning was therefore highly student driven. From the survey, it seems that
384 students appreciated this degree of freedom in the Virtual Ship Classroom.

385 3.2.2 Learning experience

386 In the survey in Cycle 2, students were asked to grade their learning experience in the
387 Virtual Ship Classroom on a scale from 1 to 10. The average grade given was a 7.5,
388 including the two grades that are “insufficient”. Below, we present derived themes from
389 our qualitative evaluation:

390 **High satisfaction with learning experience:** We can conclude that the majority of
391 students appreciated the Virtual Ship Classroom. In the open question on appreciation
392 in the student survey four students answered that they liked the experience. They said for
393 example: *“It was a very nice and interactive way to learn about planning and conducting*
394 *a research cruise and analyzing and presenting data.”* The scaffolding approach was also
395 explicitly mentioned by four students in the open question in the survey. In an interview,
396 a student elaborated on the experience:

397 *“It was quite exciting, I should say, because this is the first time I hear something about a*
398 *virtual expedition. I was somebody who wanted to go on expedition, a real expedition, in*
399 *fact. But this was really fun. [...] We just know that people go to the ocean, drop*
400 *instruments, get their data, but the pathway, how do you actually plan an expedition? You*
401 *go and you come back. Where do you drop what and things like that was actually... It was*
402 *an introduction to all of that. Yeah, it was a really nice experiment.”* [Interview student3]

403 **Collaborative learning:** Especially the instructor was very positive about the
404 collaborative learning aspect. From the TAs' observations, it also seems that it was
405 valuable for students to work together and discuss problems they encountered in groups.
406 The students themselves were critical about the group size, which was three to four in
407 Cycle 2. All four students who were interviewed said that three would be the ideal group
408 size.

409 **Ownership of roles:** Although we did not assign specific roles to the students in the
410 groups, some of the groups did this of their own accord. Students who took up a team
411 leader role managed the team and split up the team's activities. Students who took up a
412 researcher role searched for relevant information, drew conclusions from the results and
413 directed the scientific presentation. Students who took up an analyst role used the
414 notebooks to parse and analyze the acquired data. In most teams, the roles were not
415 fixed, and students switched or combined their roles. A sense of teamwork and
416 collaboration was prevalent throughout, and increased the learning experience as
417 reported in both student and staff interviews:

418 *"I was really engaged. Again, the credit goes to the group, because we all went together,*
419 *we all distributed the tasks among ourselves. Depending on what you know, what your*
420 *expertise is or what you can actually do."* [Interview Student3]

421 *"What you saw that early on, they were really all engaged and they really, they took shared*
422 *ownership of the research question of the region of the planning of the cruise. That was*
423 *really collaborative. And I guess you can only do that once, but you then one day got, once*
424 *you got the data. Many of the groups actually split out and gave different data sets to*
425 *different people, and assigned, essentially people to certain data set and said you are*
426 *going to do the analysis of the drifters, you are going to do the analysis of the CTD."*
427 [Interview Instructor]

428 3.2.3 Improvements

429 In the student survey, six students answered that the documentation of the project and
430 the possibilities of the VirtualShip package should be improved. Interviews following
431 Cycle 2 suggest improvement potential in interactive an agile planning: students should

432 be able to customize their measurement strategy depending on local conditions. Both of
433 these improvements will be taken into account in the next version of the lesson materials.

434 *“The students were more creative than I expected into what they wanted to do. And one
435 of the things that I heard a few times is to be able to deploy drifters, to base that on the
436 local conditions. [...] Yeah, agile cruising really, which we now told them that the captain
437 would just want a clear plan. And that's not true. [...] I mean, the captain and the chief
438 scientist every morning have a meeting and there's a rough cruise plan. And yeah, that
439 would be cool. I think that would be really nice for it for next year.”* [Interview Instructor]

440 *“It would be better if there can be a user interface of the VirtualShip code so that we can
441 to some extent customize our measurements (e.g., we may want to deploy the Argo floats
442 when we encounter fresh water)”* [Student survey]

443 4. Conclusion and discussion

444 In this study, we set out to evaluate the Virtual Ship Classroom as an authentic learning
445 environment that reflects real-world oceanographic research practices by investigating
446 how it impacts students' learning outcomes and experience. We evaluated this in two
447 graduate classes and found that the Virtual Ship Classroom contributes positively to
448 learning outcomes and student satisfaction.

449 Core aspects of an authentic learning activity are that the problem should mimic the work
450 of professionals, and that students are empowered through choice to direct their own
451 learning. In student-centered learning environments, students deal with difficulties,
452 learn step by step to solve problems, develop confidence in their skills, and share ideas
453 with peers (Baeten et al. 2010). The increased sense of achievement, self-confidence,
454 and self-efficacy in students confirmed that the Virtual Ship Classroom is an effective
455 learning environment. At the end of the assignment, the majority of students felt satisfied
456 of their achievements.

457 The findings from our evaluation based on students' surveys and interviews with
458 students, instructors and TAs indicate that the Virtual Ship Classroom can contribute to
459 preparing students for physical oceanography expeditions in meaningful ways. The
460 students reported high levels of engagement with the learning materials and increased

461 learning gains. They appreciated their growth in terms of content knowledge, real world
462 research planning skills, data analysis, and collaborative problem solving. The groupwork
463 dynamics introduced in Cycle 2 highlighted the importance of collaboration (among
464 other design characteristics), confirming the principles of Reeves et al. (2002) for
465 designing authentic learning activities.

466 Alongside the positive evaluation results, our investigation revealed areas for
467 improvements. Although students' self-efficacy in Python programming generally
468 increased, some expressed reduced confidence due to task complexity and insufficient
469 code documentation. This suggests a need for targeted scaffolding, especially for those
470 with limited programming experience, to ensure coding requirements support learning
471 outcomes. While students generally reported positive teamwork experiences, they
472 recommended minor adjustments to group size.

473 Limitations

474 As with any study, our research has several limitations. First, as a pilot study evaluating a
475 novel learning environment, it stands among the first empirical assessments of its kind.
476 The limited existing literature on comparable tools limits our ability to directly benchmark
477 our results, making it challenging to situate our findings within a broader context. Due to
478 the exploratory nature of this study and the limited data collected, it was not feasible to
479 derive Design Principles at this stage. While the collaborative character and authentic
480 learning environment seem to be aspects that were valued, the two cycles here limit us
481 in framing these as prominent Design Principles. A further limitation relates to the
482 participants themselves, as the study involved a relatively small group of students and
483 was specific to two graduate physical oceanography courses, limiting the generalizability
484 of our findings to other educational contexts or disciplines. Furthermore, participants
485 had varying levels of programming experience, which were not explicitly assessed, as all
486 students were expected to have a sufficient foundation in programming and the ability to
487 quickly learn Python.

488 Another limitation is that our data collection relied on self-reported measures, which may
489 introduce bias, as students might have a tendency to please interviewers and instructors
490 or may struggle to accurately self-assess their learning outcomes.

491 The authors of our study were closely involved in both the instructional design and the
492 development of the Virtual Ship Classroom to inform its structure and content. This
493 involvement reflects our positionality as both designers and researchers, which may
494 have introduced bias in the evaluation and interpretation of results.

495 Future Work

496 To tackle such limitations, future research can include a bigger sample of participants
497 across different institutions and education levels within (physical) oceanography. It
498 would be meaningful for future research to also assess the Virtual Ship Classroom's
499 effectiveness in preparing students for actual research expeditions by gathering
500 feedback from participants post-expedition. This would provide insights into what
501 aspects of the virtual experience were most helpful and identify additional features that
502 could enrich our learning environment.

503 The student feedback also suggests various improvements. Group sizes should be
504 considered, and the documentation of the code needs improvement. Fieldwork planning
505 during the activity could be made more flexible and agile by making the VirtualShip
506 package even more interactive. In addition, it would be helpful to create more narrative
507 scenarios and include Virtual Reality. And finally, include measurements beyond
508 physical oceanography, such as biogeochemical tracers and microbiology.

509 These first two cycles of the Virtual Ship Classroom have encouraged us to continue
510 developing. We will continue using the tool in the two courses described here but are
511 also planning to expand the tool to be used in other (undergraduate) courses. We aim to
512 reduce the need for prerequisite Python knowledge and therefore make the Virtual Ship
513 Classroom accessible even in secondary education courses. Other uses could be in
514 professional settings, where Principal Investigators of actual oceanographic expeditions
515 may use the VirtualShip package to plan, dry-run and optimize their expeditions. We will
516 continue to keep all development open source, so that anyone in the world can use and
517 contribute to the Virtual Ship Classroom.

518 Ethics

519 This project has received ethical approval from the Utrecht University Science-
520 Geosciences Ethics Review Board (ERB Review Bèta S-23174).

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525 Code availability

526 The code of the VirtualShip is available via virtualship.oceanparcels.org. For this study,
527 we used v0.0.2, which is archived at [10.5281/zenodo.14013932](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14013932).

528 Competing interests

529 The authors have no competing interests to declare.

530 Author's contributions

531 ED led the development of the VirtualShip package, performed the analysis and wrote the
532 first draft of the manuscript. ED and CC contributed to the instructional design of the
533 Virtual Ship Classroom, while EvS supported the development of the tool. CC and EvS
534 provided extensive feedback on the draft. We would like to thank the two anonymous
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536 References

537 Anderson, L. W., Krathwohl, D. R., Airasian, P. W., Cruikshank, K. A., Mayer, R. E.,
538 Pintrich, P. R., Raths, J., & Wittrock, M. C. (2001). *A Taxonomy for Learning,*

539 *Teaching, and Assessing: A Revision of Bloom's Taxonomy of Educational*
540 *Objectives*. New York: Longman.

541 Anderson, T., & Shattuck, J. (2012). Design-Based Research: A Decade of Progress in
542 Education Research? *Educational Researcher*, 41(1), 16–25. DOI:
543 <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X11428813>

544 Baeten, M., Kyndt, E., Struyven, K., & Dochy, F. (2010). Using student-centred learning
545 environments to stimulate deep approaches to learning: Factors encouraging or
546 discouraging their effectiveness. *Educational Research Review*, 5(3), 243–260.
547 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2010.06.001>

548 Barba, L. A., Barker, L. J., Blank, D. S., Brown, J., Downey, A., George, T., Heagy, L. J.,
549 Mandli, K., Moore, J. K., Lippert, D., Niemeyer, K., Watkins, R., West, R., Wickes,
550 E., Willing, C., & Zingale, M. (2022). Teaching and Learning with Jupyter. DOI:
551 <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.19608801.v1>

552 Barnhill, K. A., Vinha, B., Smith, A. J., de Jonge, D. S. W., Gaurisas, D. Y., Segura, R. M.,
553 Madureira, P., Albuquerque, M., Huvenne, V. A. I., Orejas, C., & Gunn, V. (2023).
554 Ship-to-shore training for active deep-sea capacity development. *ICES Journal of*
555 *Marine Science*, 80(6), 1619-1628. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsad088>

556 Cliffe, A. D. (2017). A review of the benefits and drawbacks to virtual field guides in
557 today's Geoscience higher education environment. *International Journal of*
558 *Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 14(1), 28. DOI:
559 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-017-0066-x>

560 Delandmeter, P., & van Sebille, E. (2019). The Parcels v2.0 Lagrangian framework: New
561 field interpolation schemes. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 12(8), 3571–
562 3584. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-2018-339>

563 Design-Based Research Collective. (2003). Design-Based Research: An Emerging
564 Paradigm for Educational Inquiry. *Educational Researcher*, 32(1), 5–8. DOI:
565 <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X032001005>

566 Fiomumwe, T. (2022). Exploring the opportunities of virtual fieldwork in teaching
567 geography during COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Geography and*
568 *Geography Education*, 45, 76–87. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.32003/igge.973983>

569 Gaillard, F., Diverres, D., Jacquin, S., Gouriou, Y., Grelet, J., Le Menn, M., Tassel, J., &
570 Reverdin, G. (2015). Sea surface temperature and salinity from French research
571 vessels, 2001–2013. *Scientific Data*, 2(1), 150054. DOI:
572 <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2015.54>

573 Gerringer, M. E., Ismail, Y., Cannon, K. A., Camilo Hernández, A., Gonzales Peralta, F.,
574 Bohlen, R., Cartwright, J. C., Feasley, A., Fregosi, L., Lehman, H., Niles, H., Quay,
575 J., Sherpa, N., Woodworth, B. H., & Cantwell, K. (2023). Deep-sea biology in
576 undergraduate classrooms: Open access data from remotely operated vehicles
577 provide impactful research experiences. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 9. DOI:
578 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.1033274>

579 Glenn, S., Schofield, O., Kohut, J., McDonnell, J., Ludescher, R., Seidel, D., Aragon, D.,
580 Haskins, T., Handel, E., Haldeman, C., Heifetz, I., Kerfoot, J., Lemus, E.,
581 Lichtenwalner, S., Ojanen, L., Roarty, H., Carvalho, F., Lopez, A., Martin, A., ...
582 Fanjul, E. (2011). The Trans-Atlantic Slocum Glider Expeditions: A Catalyst for

583 Undergraduate Participation in Ocean Science and Technology. *Marine*
584 *Technology Society Journal*, 45(1), 52–67. DOI:
585 <https://doi.org/10.4031/MTSJ.45.1.12>

586 GOPAF (2024). Global Ocean Physics Analysis and Forecast. (n.d.). Retrieved April 12,
587 2024, from
588 [https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/GLOBAL_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_](https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/GLOBAL_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_001_024/description)
589 [001_024/description](https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/GLOBAL_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_001_024/description)

590 Gunn, V., & Thomsen, L. (2009). The Next Generation: Providing Inspiration and Training
591 for Future Marine Scientists. *Oceanography*, 22(1), 166–176.

592 Henrie, C. R., Halverson, L. R., & Graham, C. R. (2015). Measuring student engagement
593 in technology-mediated learning: A review. *Computers and Education*, 90, 36–
594 53. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2015.09.005>

595 Herrington, J., Reeves, T. C., & Oliver, R. (2013). Authentic Learning Environments. In J.
596 M. Spector, M. D. Merrill, J. Elen, & M. J. Bishop (Eds.), *Handbook of Research on*
597 *Educational Communications and Technology* (pp. 401–412). Springer. DOI:
598 https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-3185-5_32

599 Herrington, T., & Herrington, J. (2005). *Authentic Learning Environments in Higher*
600 *Education*. Information Science Publishing.

601 Johnson, J. W. (2020). Benefits and Pitfalls of Jupyter Notebooks in the Classroom.
602 *Proceedings of the 21st Annual Conference on Information Technology*
603 *Education*, 32–37. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3368308.3415397>

604 Kahu, E. R. (2013). Framing student engagement in higher education. *Studies in Higher*
605 *Education*, 38(5), 758–773. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2011.598505>

606 Koenigstein, S., Hentschel, L.-H., Heel, L. C., & Drinkorn, C. (2020). A game-based
607 education approach for sustainable ocean development. *ICES Journal of Marine*
608 *Science*, 77(5), 1629–1638. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsaa035>

609 Kuroda, Y., Kai, G., & Okuno, K. (1988). Development of a shipboard acoustic Doppler
610 current profiler. *OCEANS '88. "A Partnership of Marine Interests"*. Proceedings,
611 353–358 vol.2. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/OCEANS.1988.23527>

612 Lumpkin, R., & Pazos, M. (2005). Measuring surface currents with Surface Velocity
613 Program drifters: The instrument, its data, and some recent results. In Jr. Kirwan
614 A. D., A. Griffa, A. J. Mariano, H. T. Rossby, & T. Özgökmen (Eds.), *Lagrangian*
615 *Analysis and Prediction of Coastal and Ocean Dynamics* (pp. 39–67). Cambridge
616 University Press. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511535901.003>

617 Mayer, I., Zhou, Q., Keijser, X., & Abspoel, L. (2014). Gaming the Future of the Ocean:
618 The Marine Spatial Planning Challenge 2050. In M. Ma, M. F. Oliveira, & J.
619 Baalsrud Hauge (Eds.), *Serious Games Development and Applications* (pp. 150–
620 162). Springer International Publishing. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-11623-5_13)
621 [11623-5_13](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-11623-5_13)

622 Mayring, P. (2014). *Qualitative content analysis: Theoretical foundation, basic*
623 *procedures and software solution*.

624 Naul, E., & Liu, M. (2019). Why Story Matters: A Review of Narrative in Serious Games.
625 *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 58(3). DOI:
626 <https://doi.org/10.1177/0735633119859904>

627 Papert, S. (1980). *Mindstorms: Children, computers, and powerful ideas*. Basic Books,
628 Inc.

629 Piaget, J. (1954). *The Construction Of Reality In The Child*. Routledge. DOI:
630 <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315009650>

631 Reeves, T. (2006). Design research from a technology perspective. In *Educational*
632 *Design Research*. Routledge.

633 Reeves, T. C., Herrington, J., & Oliver, R. (2002). Authentic activities and online learning.
634 *Quality Conversations: Research and Development in Higher Education*, 25,
635 562–567.

636 Resnick, M., Myers, B., Nakakoji, K., Shneiderman, B., Pausch, R., Selker, T., &
637 Eisenberg, M. (2005). *Design Principles for Tools to Support Creative Thinking*.
638 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1184/R1/6621917.v1>

639 Rule, A. C. (2006). The components of authentic learning.
640 <http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12648/7426>

641 Timmermann, A., An, S.-I., Kug, J.-S., Jin, F.-F., Cai, W., Capotondi, A., Cobb, K. M.,
642 Lengaigne, M., McPhaden, M. J., Stuecker, M. F., Stein, K., Wittenberg, A. T., Yun,
643 K.-S., Bayr, T., Chen, H.-C., Chikamoto, Y., Dewitte, B., Dommenges, D., Grothe,
644 P., Guilyardi, E., Ham, Y.-G., Hayashim, M., Ineson, S., Kang, D., Kim, S., Kim, W.,
645 Lee, J.-Y., Li, T., Luo, J.-J., McGregor, S., Planton, Y., Power, S., Rashid, H., Ren, H.-
646 L., Santoso, A., Takahashi, K., Todd, A., Wang, G., Wang, G., Xie, R., Yang, W.-H.,
647 Yeh, S.-W., Yoon, J., Zeller, E., & Zhang, X. (2018). El Niño–Southern Oscillation
648 complexity. *Nature*, 559(7715), 535–545. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-018-0252-6)
649 [018-0252-6](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-018-0252-6)

650 Wong, A. P. S., Wijffels, S. E., Riser, S. C., Pouliquen, S., Hosoda, S., Roemmich, D.,
651 Gilson, J., Johnson, G. C., Martini, K., Murphy, D. J., Scanderbeg, M., Bhaskar, T. V.
652 S. U., Buck, J. J. H., Merceur, F., Carval, T., Maze, G., Cabanes, C., André, X.,
653 Poffa, N., ... Park, H.-M. (2020). Argo Data 1999–2019: Two Million Temperature-
654 Salinity Profiles and Subsurface Velocity Observations From a Global Array of
655 Profiling Floats. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 7. DOI:
656 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2020.00700>

657 Xiao, S., Zhang, M., Liu, C., Jiang, C., Wang, X., & Yang, F. (2023). CTD Sensors for Ocean
658 Investigation Including State of Art and Commercially Available. *Sensors*, 23(2).
659 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23020586>

660